

BIO-SUSHY

Sustainable surface protection by glass-like hybrid and biomaterials coatings

Deliverable D.2.1

Bio-based thermoplastic powder coating

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Publishable Summary

The Deliverable *D.2.1 "Bio-based thermoplastic powder coating"* is presented in this document and aims summarizing the developed organic powder coating formulations covering their production as well as applications on the selected paper substrates.

The document is organized into different sections:

- 1) Task objectives
- 2) Description of powder coating formulation preparation, characterization and application
- 3) Toxicity Measurements and related results
- 4) Conclusions

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Table of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
FTIR	Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy
MeOH	Methanol
PBS	Polybutylene succinate
PHA	Polyhydroxyalkanoates
PHBV	Poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate)
SEM	Scanning Electron Microscopy
SSbD	Safety and Sustainability by Design
UWG	Under Water Granulate System

1. Objectives

This deliverable covers the production of organic powder coating materials, 150g per different formulation, developed within BIO-SUSHY project under task WP2 Task 2.1 (main characteristics defined in Table 1). The prepared powder coatings are being characterized in respect to their physico-chemical properties as shown in the paragraphs below. Further, coated paper substrates are characterized in respect to their previously identified Key Performance Indicators.

Table 1: BIO-SUSHY organic powder coatings main characteristics

BIO-SUSHY Coating materials	% biobased	Ratio inorganic/organic	Solvent	Application process
Biobased powder coating (Wood K plus)	formulation content: >80%	90-100% organic	0% (powder coating)	Powder spray; Gelling temperatures: 80 to max. 200 °C; Gelling time: 5 to 30 sec.

2. Description

2.1. General characteristics of the demonstrator

In this section the preparation and characterization of the demonstrators carried out by WOOD K PLUS in collaboration with SIKEMIA is shown in more detail, covering the production method of 150g powder coating material, for different formulations. Based on the results shown and discussed in the following paragraphs are shown the 3 different pictures of the best-performing powder coating formulations (see figures Figure 1, Figure 2, Figure 3). The demonstrators cover *PHA Type 1* powder coating (Figure 1), *Lignin Type 1* powder coating modified by SIKEMIA (Figure 2), and *PBS Type1* based formulation with high *Lignin Type 2* content (Figure 3).

Figure 1: DEMONSTRATOR 1: *PHA Type 1* powder coating (= virgin PHA powder with additives) packed in a plastic bag (size:11x18cm) (left) and powder spray coated paper substrate (right; size 8x12cm)

Figure 2: DEMONSTRATOR 2: *Lignin Type 1* powder coating = Modified Lignin powder (Hydrophobic Lignin with *n*-octyltiethoxysilane modification done by Sikemia) packed in a plastic bag (size:11x18cm) (left) and powder spray coated paper substrate (right; size 8x12cm)

Figure 3: DEMONSTRATOR 3: *PBS Type1/ Lignin Type2* powder coating (= PBS based formulations with Lignin Type 2) packed in plastic bags (size:11x18cm) (high lignin content); prepared granulate (left), powder coating (after grinding; middle) and coated paper (right; size: 8x12cm)

2.1.1: Organic powder coatings manufacturing

For the production of different thermoplastic powder coatings under Task 2.1 the following procedure has been used. Thermoplastic powder coatings made of thermoplastic resins like different types of PHA and PBS biopolymers are combined with additives - plasticizers, temperature stabilizers and natural polymers different lignin types (in this report shown under following names *Lignin Type 1* (modified by SIKEMIA within the project), *Lignin Type 2* (available at pre-commercial scale)) considering different blending ratios using gravimetric dosing and extruded using laboratory scale twin screw extruder Brabender TSE20 (20 mm in screw diameter). The extruded material was pelletized using an Under Water Granulating (UWG) System as shown below in Figure 4. Produced granulates are further crushed using grinder and screened to gain powder (see Figure 5) of prepared coatings targeting a specific particle size distribution up to 150 µm in diameter. Powder coating is a 100% solids content applied as a dry powder (after grinding) and subsequently formed into a film with heat using a laboratory press machine (illustration is given in Figure 7).

Figure 4: Twin screw extrusion (melt compounding) of thermoplastic powder coatings at Wood K plus, extruder shown starting from left followed by prepared granulates

Figure 5: Granulates grinded to powders by centrifugal mill (left) and further sieved (middle); Right: granulates before grinding and sieving as well in final powder form

2.1.2: Lignin modification by SIKEMIA

Within BIO-SUSHY, the functionalization of selected commercial kraft lignin, UPM BioPiva, has been achieved using an alkoxy silane with a long alkyl chain to chemically modify the lignin to provide water repellency. Figure 6 provides a schematic overview, of the lignin functionalization procedure (*Lignin Type 1*).

Figure 6: Functionalization of Lignin with C8 Silane grafting function (*n*-octyltriethoxysilane)

This modification may also improve lignin compatibility with non-polar matrices in the case lignin is being applied as an additive in powder coating formulations. Characterization of modified lignin powder have been done using Methoxyl Group determination, MeOH Nb and Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR).

Methoxyl Group Determination results are displayed in the Table 2 below.

Table 2: Methoxyl Group Determination results done at Wood K plus

Samples	weight mg	MeO				Content MeO %	MeO mmol/g
		Area	MeI mol	Mass MeO mg	Content MeO		
KC-2192 UPM BioPiva_01	11.28	3692212	5.16E-02	1.60E+00	14.19	4.58	
KC-2192 UPM BioPiva_02	14.62	4152139	5.81E-02	1.80E+00	12.31	3.97	
KC-2192 UPM BioPiva_03	12.03	3544293	4.96E-02	1.54E+00	12.77	4.12	
KC-2192 UPM deriv_01	12.77	1265938	1.77E-02	5.49E-01	4.30	1.39	
KC-2192 UPM deriv_02	13.19	1633887	2.28E-02	7.08E-01	5.37	1.73	
KC-2192 UPM deriv_03	14.59	1564911	2.19E-02	6.78E-01	4.65	1.50	

The FTIR results are not shown here.

2.1.3: Organic powder coatings application

The prepared powder coating formulations are spray-coated onto selected paper substrates as described in the next paragraph.

Selected paper substrate, provided by ECOZEMA, was horizontally positioned in the powder spray booth and sprayed with the coating powder electrostatically (one side). The applied powder particle film was gelled and "smoothed" using a hot press. Figure 7 shows the spray coating trials at various stages to obtain coated papers.

Figure 7: Powder coating experiments set up

Figure 8 to Figure 10 show coating results on Inverform paper substrate using different powder coating formulations (selected pictures).

Figure 8: Coated selected paper substrate with PHA Type 1

Figure 9: Coated paper substrate with Modified lignin by SIKEMIA (Lignin Type 2)

Figure 10: Coated selected paper substrate with PBS Type1/Lignin Type 2 powder coating

2.2. Physico-chemical characteristics of the organic powder coating material

The prepared powders are characterized in respect to their melting temperatures T_m using Differential Scanning Calorimetry DSC. The DSC diagrams are not shown here. The following T_m are recorded: PBS powder type 2: 115°C, PHA dependent on the copolymer type, 133°C to 176°C.

2.2.1 Particle Size Distribution (PSD):

Before spray coating experiments sieve analysis of the PHA and PBS selected thermoplastic matrices has been done. The results are shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11 Particle size distribution of PHA (left) and PBS powder (right) using sieve analysis

As can be seen from Figure 11, a very broad particle size distribution has been found considering PHA powder (original powder supplied by the producer). In parallel, a narrow particle size distribution have been shown for PBS powder. After sieve analysis, the results of the different powder fractions have been investigated by using light microscopy. Figure 12 and Figure 13 show the light microscopy done for PHA thermoplastic powders, as well as PBS powder being used as matrix materials in other powder coating formulations.

Figure 12: Light microscopy micrographs showing different sieve fractions (particle sizes) after PHA powder sieve analysis

Figure 13: Light microscopy micrographs showing different sieve fractions (particle sizes) after PBS powder sieve analysis

2.2.2 Coating hardness

Organic powder coatings based on PHA thermoplastic matrices like PHBV (Short-chain length PHAs (scl-PHAs)) and PHBH (medium-chain-length (mcl-PHAs)) tested here are have a Shore D hardness of approximately 60-61. Further, organic powder coatings formulations based on PBS (Polybutylene Succinate) hardness score are generally in the range of 30-65 Shore D. The specific hardness can vary based on factors like crystallinity (different PHA types are tested within BIO-SUSHY project) and the presence of additives e.g., natural polymers studied here like lignin.

2.2.3 Scanning Electron Microscopy of coated papers

After application of prepared thermoplastic powders on paper substrates (size: up to A3) by spray technology the inspection of the coated surfaces is being done by Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM). Figure 14 show SEM micrographs of some coated papers using bioplastics like PHA and PBS polymers as well as paper substrate used in the coating trials.

Figure 14: Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) micrographs form paper substrates (left, 100µm scale), PBS based powder coated paper (middle, 100µm scale) and PHA based coated paper (right, 100 µm scale)

After application of prepared thermoplastic powders on paper substrates by spray technology the coated papers are characterized in respect to water contact angle, Gurley measurements, KIT rating (grease resistance according to ISO 16532-2), water repellency and water absorption (Cobb Test).

Methods being used here for paper characterization are described briefly below.

Contact angle measurement: Device: DataPhysics OCA 35E; Measurement → Methodology: Sessile drop method - static contact angle; Test liquid: water, ethylene glycol, diiodomethane; Drop volume: 1.5 µl; Drop rate: 1 µl/s; Analysis method: Ellipse Fitting; Manual setting of the baseline

KIT rating: Grease resistance according to ISO 16532-2

Gurley measurements: Device: Air Permeance Tester Gurley Type (Tecnolab); Measurement → Methodology: acc. EN ISO 5636-5; 5 repeat measurements per sample

"Water repellency": 1) water droplet (ca. 0,1 ml) dropped on the horizontal surface; 2) surface positioned at an angle of 45° to 60° 3) observation of run-off behaviour

Water absorption: 1) punch out samples (diameter 50mm); 2) condition at 23°C/50%rIF; 3) measure weight; 4) pour water into small plastic cup (height always the same) and place on sample; 5) remove cup after 2h and lightly dab sample; 6) measure weight and visually assess whether water is absorbed.

Figure 15: Photos of tests carried out on coated samples (from left to right): contact angle measurements; KIT; Gurley; water repellency.

Table 3 shows the main results achieved in respect to water and oil repellency of different coated papers and following Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) identified for food packaging case study by the project partner ECOZEMA.

Table 3: Results covering contact angle measurements, KIT rating, Gurley measurements, Cobb Test, Water repellency covering different powder coating formulations

Powder coating formulation	Contact angle measurements									KIT (Grease)	Gurley-measurements					"Water repellency" (water droplet on an inclined surface - 45° to 60°)	Water absorption test "Cobb" 2h [g/m²]
	Water		Ethylene glycol		Diiodomethane		Total surface energy [mN/m]	Disperse part [mN/m]	Polar part [mN/m]		Kit rating	1	2	3	4		
	CA [°]	STD	CA [°]	STD	CA [°]	STD											
No coating	118	4	83	8	71	1	23,69	23,54	0,15	1	22s	22s	23s	24s	24s	water penetration	144
PHA 1	79	1	60	4	48	5	35,82	31,17	4,66	12	*(1)	*(1)	*(1)	*(1)	*(1)	water repellent	55
Lignin 1	104	2	64	1	56	2	32,89	32,84	0,05	-	*(1)	*(1)	*(1)	*(1)	*(1)	water repellent	17
PBS1/Lignin2	81	7	51	3	29	2	43,29	40,84	2,45	12	*(1)	*(1)	*(1)	*(1)	*(1)	water repellent	19

*1) The measurement is not possible. It seems that the air can not go through the sample!

3. Toxicity testing of coating components

To study potential impact of human exposure during the coating production (following Step 1 and 2 of Safety and Sustainability by Design (SSbD) Framework) toxicity assessment (cytotoxicity) is done by ITENE. This covers studying the cell viability by using MTT assay (please see Figure 16) to measure metabolic activity of the prepared powder coatings as well as the individual components of powders

coatings to ensure safety from an early R&D coating design phase. Table 4 displays the cytotoxicity results from PHA (PHA Type 1), PBS (PBS Type1) and Modified lignin (Lignin Type 2) studied here. Figure 17 shows the cell viability by MTT assay from tested modified lignin. For other tested materials the results are shown only within Table 4.

Figure 16 Cell viability by MTT assay studied at ITENE

Table 4: Toxicological studies (cytotoxicity) results covering tested PHA type (PHA Type1), PBS (PBS Type 1) and modified lignin by SIKEMIA within BIO-SUSHY project

Sample	Cell line	EC ₅₀
Paper Substrate from WoodK+ pH 4 60°C 05h	A549	> 100 ppm
	CaCo-2	> 100 ppm
	HaCaT	> 100 ppm
Coated Paper Substrate from WoodK+ pH 4 60°C 05h PHBV Coating	A549	> 100 ppm
	CaCo-2	> 100 ppm
	HaCaT	> 100 ppm
Coated Paper Substrate from WoodK+ pH 4 60°C 05h PBS Coating	A549	> 100 ppm
	CaCo-2	> 100 ppm
	HaCaT	> 100 ppm
Cuprinol Leachate pH 7,4 60°C 24h	A549	> 100 ppm
	CaCo-2	> 100 ppm
	HaCaT	> 100 ppm
Lignin C8 (SIKEMIA) Hydrophobic	A549	> 100 ppm
	CaCo-2	> 100 ppm
	HaCaT	> 100 ppm
Carnauba Wax	A549	> 100 ppm
	CaCo-2	> 100 ppm
	HaCaT	> 100 ppm
UPB PIVA 100	A549	> 100 ppm
	CaCo-2	> 100 ppm
	HaCaT	> 100 ppm

Figure 17: Toxicological results of the Lignin C8 modified by SIKEMIA (Lignin Type1)

Further, for step 3, to experimentally assess the risk of BIO-SUSHY coatings materials when it comes to the use phase, a biomembrane sensor coupled with a minirelease accelerator within an online configuration at University Leeds is being used to measure potential.

Figure 18: (a) RCV scan of lipid layer sensor in the absence (black) and in the presence of 0.009 % modified lignin (red) in the phosphate buffered saline at 40 Vs-1; (b) Percentage peak suppression in the presence of coating material carnauba wax (CW), PBS (PBS Type1), PHBV (PHA Type1) and modified lignin (Lignin Type1) at concentrations displayed on the bar graph; (c) from leachates arising from coated papers in phosphate buffer saline at 20 °C (yellow) and 70 °C (green)

The results displayed in Figure 18 showed that compared to the control test no evidence of the significant release from the different studied coatings based on modified lignin, PBS and PHA thermoplastic matrices is observed. Still, some differences in the biomembrane activity between different coated papers are recognized.

4. Conclusions

Different thermoplastic powder coating formulations have been developed to potentially replace PFAS compounds used in paper coating targeting water and oil repellency (grease resistance). The paper samples coated with PBS/lignin and PHA based formulations by spray exhibit hydrophobic properties (as shown in water absorption tests, with some promising results for Cobb tests) and very good results for KIT rating (grease resistance) without the use of PFAS. Bio-based content of different thermoplastic powder coatings presented here may vary from 80-90% for PBS based coatings with lignin (lignin loadings from 30-40 weight percentage loading and having PBS as matrix polymer with 50 % bio-based content). Further, formulations based on PHA are up to 98% bio-based (2 weight percent of additives inside). The certification on bio-based content of different PHA types used here are available as an official document from PHA producers. Regarding the use of natural polymers, such as different lignin types being used in some powder coating formulations as additives, a full toxicity assessment is being conducted following the SSbD Framework. The powder coatings should be applied on one side of the paper. The storage conditions recommended are dry storage at <math><25^{\circ}\text{C}</math>, up to 2 years.

Since the powder coatings studied here are targeting food packaging applications, migration tests, compostability and repulping (recycling) are planned to be covered following current regulations for the paper and packaging sector. In addition, during the upcoming scale-up phase of the BIO-SUSHY coating formulations the selected thermoplastic powder coating formulations will be tested with respect to their processability, focusing on extrusion coating and/or dry powder coating technologies of paper.

